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Exploring The Relationship Between Priceless Laptop Scheme & Socio – Economic Development Among Undergraduate Students

T.Sundararasan, Prof.G.Kalaiyaran, R.Udhaya Mohan Babu, X.Arockia Anita, Sohel Rana Sarkar

Abstract: Education, apart from encompassing both teaching and learning, encompasses nice social importance, particularly within the fashionable, advanced industrialized societies. The most important social objective of education is to complete the socialization method which guarantees the symmetrical growth of physical, mental and spiritual aspects of individuals. The utilization of technology in education has increased the quality in our education system. This paper estimates the impact of Priceless Laptop Computer Scheme of Government of Tamil Nadu to the students of government and aided schools and its role in the socio-economic development of undergraduate students. The analysis reveals that the welfare scheme facilitates access to top-quality studies and it causes socio-economic development among vulnerable, deprived youth, principally from a rural background, increasing with the timely access to academic requirement, to higher levels of study, and studies abroad. The welfare scheme's cooperative approach holds promise for scaling up this and similar efforts to extend establishment participation among youth in Tamilnadu and alternative locations. In recent years, the implementation of innovative schemes from the government has allowed creating an impact on the financial aid of the primary way of education. In this sense, the introduction of technology on education at the state level allowed learners with digital acquisition and their potential skills to use those skills within the geographic point reciprocally for the next level. Finally, the introduction of schemes can even facilitate to cut back the human workforce indirectly. In summary, the social and economic impact of conversion indicates an important contribution to education growth and price improvement. On the opposite hand, job creation effects seem to take issue by trade aspect.

Keywords: Empowerment, Higher Education, Priceless Laptop Scheme, Social Development, Technology, Undergraduate Students, Welfare Scheme

I. INTRODUCTION

To develop social intelligence to crack issues of economic security, a program of education should be planned to supply for 2 teams of objectives. The primary one could be a general understanding of the character and purpose of the national economy. The second cluster of objectives is that the realization of the social principles. Admitting the inadequacy of the current college programme for the accomplishment of those objectives, it's pertinent to counsel some modifications that may facilitate a lot of study of social and economic issues (Suresh Dutt, 2005). Receiving a decent education helps empower students, to understand the socio-economic problem that leads to perceive the much needed solution to any given state of affairs. It's solely understood that they will simply avail rights as a subject and for improvement within the structural functioning of governance and economy. Education helps students perceive themselves higher, it helps students understand their potential and qualities as an individual's being (Vanraj.V.Parmar, 2017). Learning through computers improves performance at examinations, develops downside resolution skills and increases student's satisfaction.

In the past decades, there has been a revolution in our society which has been done by modernization of education with capitalising the technological progress into it and it'll be moving at a fast pace. Economic and environmental issues show few signs of improvement for a student in the current situation. Encumbering external support levels, weak development and real growth typically getting in a standard of living, damaging relationship with society and degradation to the standard of living activity. Today, innovations in instructional system square measure is having wide-ranging effects across various domains of society, and policymaker's measure working on problems involving economic productivity, privacy protection, and affordability of access to data. Our instructional system created currently can have womb-to-tomb consequences and a spotlight should be paid to their social and economic impacts. One in each of the foremost important outcomes of the progress of an instructional system may be e-learning over the web, a replacement manner of learning. It affects such massive sectors as ladies, backward and helpless communities and may expand to areas like the instructional analysis. Advances in technology can affect the craft of teaching by complementing instead of eliminating ancient room instruction. The best potential for brand new technology lies in raising the productivity of the time spent outside the classroom. Creating solutions to drawback sets and appointed reading materials offered on the net offers tons of convenience. E-mail immensely simplifies communication between students and school could also be engaged in the cluster comes. Another vital manner is that technology on education is reducing the importance of distance in learning. In several establishments, the geographic distribution of education is considerably dynamic. As an example, some e-contents have found that they will overcome the tight native issue for advanced learning by causing e-contents to others wherever they want. Moreover, such arrangements, most of the times, will result in variations so that it is worked on nearly round the

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clock. E-Contents will manage the student's learning, wherever they want. Therefore, the technology on education will alter a finer division of learners among countries that successively affects the relative demand for numerous skills in every nation. The technology on education allows monumental labour and employment to be decoupled from each other. Priceless Laptop scheme involves student's usage, learning through technology and perform basic operations in an exceedingly portable computer. It's typically outlined the essential information of associate degree skills required to work on packaged products like a software package, a packaged application, or an automatic internet style tool. Government of Tamil Nadu has entrusted the work of procedure of Laptops presently with Lenovo. The recipient students must have domicile of the state of Tamil Nadu and must belong to the Government and Government Aided schools.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Radhika Kapur (2018) attempted to perceive the socio-economic development and management of underprivileged teams. Scheduled Castes, Tribes and alternative backward categories represent the underprivileged teams. Socio-economic development and management of underprivileged teams is an indispensable space that has to be taken into thought to steer to effective growth and development of the country. It's primarily involved with transportation concerning improvement within the system of education, employment opportunities, lifestyles, incomes, skills development, and cultural factors. Schemes are initiated to bring them on par with the broader community. The issues of impoverishment, illiteracy, and state are the key barriers at intervals, the course of their socio-economic development and management. The government has enforced varied programs and schemes that facilitate education, employment opportunities, financial gain generation and overall sustenance of their living conditions. The processes of social and economic transformations are primarily based on cultural and environmental factors. Gangadhar Dahal (2016) investigated the linkages between education and varied socio-economic parameters in the Asian country. The study reveals that enhancements in education have a positive impact on the lives through improvement in personal competencies, a direction towards redoubled employment and financial gain, higher quality of living, sweetening of awareness concerning several dimensions of life, community, and nation, and additional meaning of participation of individuals in socio-economic activities. It additionally shows that investment in education to extend the economic process, ladies' direction jointly type of human development strategy, has gained economists' and policymakers' interest. On the opposite aspect, it establishes human capital that produces a considerable contribution to the growth of economic and financial gain. Its contribution returns within the type of expert human resources World Health Organization will contribute and lead in reducing personal income. The article evaluates varied analysis findings on the contributions created by the education sector on the economic process. This paper initiates the discussion on the role of education in socio-economic changes and the way education will foster economic process and socio-economic development.

Similarly, the middle half focuses on the challenges of the education system in terms of quality and market desires particularly in developing countries like Asian countries. Similarly, it deals with the reforms taken throughout the past few years within the education system in developing countries like Asian countries and alternative developed countries once millennium development goals launched. At last, this analysis recommends some necessary problems, that square measure associated with policy reform in education and alternative associated sectors. Ishu Chadda & Vikram Chadha (2017) concluded from their research that human welfare is the central part of the economic development of a contemporary economy. That's why since independence the welfare of the plenty discovered and each tool and objective of Indian policy. At independence, the Asian nation hereditary a quickly growing population, food deprivation, rampant poorness, content associated illiteracy of plenty associated an overall unbalanced and decadent socio-economic antecedent of a jap society. Still, the planners were aware to the truth that unless the fruits of economic process percolate down to rock bottom runs of the society, real development and welfare are nonsense. The Nehruvian/Mahalanobis model, continuing until the Fourth set up, followed the trickle-down approach i.e. to surge the momentum of growth with massive monolithic investment and capital formation and accomplish high financial gain growth specified the high financial gain can ad libitum trickle down to lower strata. An agreement emerged that the event policy required to pursue a high rate of growth or per capita financial gain in conjunction with additional until towards the social objectives i.e. employment generation and alleviation of poorness. Thus, 2 discreetly otherwise strands of development approaches emerged, one the Nehruvian trickle-down approach i.e. growth preceding equity and distribution of financial gain through wage and employment generation programmes, whereas the opposite approach the subunit and Derze model of growth hinges on the social sector development, associate approach that is associate adjunct to the aptitude approach and advocates human and social development however continuing high growth. It professes to make employment opportunities and engagement of the disadvantaged and marginal segments. This approach to development is imperative for directly eliminating the poorness and creating growth comprehensive. The event economists and policymakers are unanimous in their readers that the event of the social sector is most vital for accelerated economic development with adequate stress on social justice. Valmiki Krishna & Rudrappa Shashidhar (2014) found that the Asian nation is a nation of villages. It's preponderantly associate agricultural country wherever regarding 70% of the individual's area unit dependent upon the land for his or her living and seventy-five percent sleep in rural Asian nation. Indian villages area unit tormented by economic distress because of the lower per capita financial gain, illiteracy and wide unfold deficiency disease and undernutrition. They conjointly suffer from the absence of basic amenities like higher housing facilities, transportation and communication services. Visible of the recommendations of the commission appointed from time to time under the policies and programmes enforced from government and alternative agencies for socio-economic development of rural individuals, the paper explores

government initiatives, implications and explores the connotations of development of rural individuals. Further, the manuscript seeks to look at, explores the financial condition in the nation with interest in rural population and analysis of the programmes and policies and implementation of welfare programmes notably. Finally, the paper concludes wipe-out of financial condition in rural nations and the extent of improvement of living of rural individuals and achievements of the commitments created by the govt. and alternative agencies in rewarding conditions of the economic process. A shot is additionally created to counsel the ways that to extend girl's management of rural people's economic development which could be an actuation of the rural economy.

III. DATA AND METHODS

Using knowledge on the first cohorts of tertiary students, this study aims to explore the link between priceless laptop scheme and socio-economic development among college students. This deals with the routine adopted by the researcher to analyse to hit the expected outcome. In this current era, socio-economic development has a crucial role to play in the country's growth. A perceived lack of socio-economic development is seen as a symptom that the student doesn't possess the application skills and supports for effective development. Student development is a vital obligation of the syllabus at academic establishments, the coaching that starts at the elementary level. The very fact is that the majority of the scholars fail to accumulate competency in development even in once at faculty levels. The doors of world opportunities for private and skilled growth stay closed before them because of their incapability to prove themselves in day to day life. Individual development is a vital ingredient for fulfilment in any action. The absence of or unknowingness regarding development is the result of growing compromise with the standard of individual and country's growth. The population of this analysis was the college students of Kancheepuram district. The investigator is a resident of Kancheepuram District, Tamil Nadu, and he chose a specific sample from college students in Kancheepuram District. The sample size was 605 and convenient sampling was adopted within the study. Students of rural backgrounds were most well-preferred as a sample with an understanding that, relatively, they are part of specific concepts in socio-economic development. To confirm the homogeneity and also the adequate representations, square measure is given to factors like gender, stream, neighbourhood and parent's academic level. The major aim of the current study is to implement and search out the link between priceless laptop scheme and socio-economic development among college students. Generally, analysis issues have totally different ways for the investigation. Methodology strategy followed in the study is normative survey method. The variables studied fair amount of socio-economic development. The analysis is constructed on a survey of college students, who had received the laptop through the government welfare scheme. The impact analysis focuses on the tertiary program at the college level. The information utilized in the analysis return from a survey of college students were conjointly thought about for the scheme. The investigator obtained the information to

spot and get in touch with candidates from varied academic instructional establishments. Survey analysis provides a scientific and logical technique of respondent to the questions. It's the foremost subtle, actual and powerful technique of discovering and developing an organized body of knowledge domain. For a collection of pertinent information, the investigator used Socio-Economic Development form and it was developed and Standardized by the investigator along-side his analysis supervisor and validated by the sphere specialists that were administered to gather the information. The collected information for the variables are analysed by Correlation Analysis.

IV. RESULTS

Testing of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant relationship between management and gender in the relationship between priceless laptop scheme and socio-economic development among the undergraduate students of Kancheepuram.

Table 1

S.No	Variables	N	Mean	SD	Management	Gender
1.	Management	605	2.64	.646	1	0.130**
2.	Gender	605	1.49	.500	0.130**	1

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant relationship between management and locality in the relationship between priceless laptop scheme and socio-economic development among the undergraduate students of Kancheepuram.

Table 2

S.No	Variables	N	Mean	SD	Management	Locality
1.	Management	605	2.64	.646	1	-0.018
2.	Locality	605	1.21	.411	-.018	1

Hypothesis 3

There is no significant relationship between management and stream in the relationship between priceless laptop scheme and socio-economic development among the undergraduate students of Kancheepuram.

Table 3

S.No	Variables	N	Mean	SD	Management	Stream
1.	Management	605	2.64	0.646	1	0.192**
2.	Stream	605	1.72	0.831	0.192**	1

Hypothesis 4

There is no significant relationship between gender and locality in the relationship between priceless laptop scheme and socio-economic development among the undergraduate students of Kancheepuram.

Table 4

S.No.	Variables	N	Mean	SD	Gender	Locality
1.	Gender	605	1.49	0.500	1	0.47
2.	Locality	605	1.21	0.411	0.47	1

Hypothesis 5

There is no significant relationship between gender and stream in the relationship between priceless laptop scheme and socio-economic development among the undergraduate students of Kancheepuram.

Table 5

S.No.	Variables	N	Mean	SD	Gender	Stream
1.	Gender	605	1.49	0.500	1	0.11
2.	Stream	605	1.72	0.831	0.11	1

Hypothesis 6

There is no significant relationship between locality and stream in the relationship between priceless laptop scheme and socio-economic development among the undergraduate students of Kancheepuram.

Table 6

S.No.	Variables	N	Mean	SD	Locality	Stream
1.	Locality	605	1.21	0.411	1	-0.96*
2.	Stream	605	1.72	0.831	-0.96*	1

Findings

Table 1 to 6 indicate the correlation values for variables in the relationship between priceless laptop scheme and socio-economic development among the undergraduate students of Kancheepuram. From hypothesis 1, the calculated correlation value for the management and gender is 0.130, which is significant at 0.01 level of significance. The result shows positive correlation between management and gender. Thus management increases similarly the gender also increases. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. From hypothesis 2, the calculated correlation value for the management and locality is -0.018 which is not significant at 0.01 level of significance. The result shows negative correlation between management and locality. Thus, management increases but the locality decreases. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted. From hypothesis 3, the calculated correlation value for the management and stream is 0.192 which is significant at 0.01 level of significance. The result shows positive correlation between management and stream. Thus, management increases similarly the stream also increases. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. From hypothesis 4, the calculated correlation value for the gender and locality is 0.47 which is not significant at 0.01 level of significance. The result shows negative correlation between gender and locality. Thus, gender increases but locality decreases. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted. From hypothesis 5, the calculated correlation value for the gender and stream is 0.11 which is not significant at 0.01 level of significance. The result shows negative correlation between gender and stream. Thus, gender increases but stream decreases. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted. From hypothesis 6, the calculated correlation value for the locality and stream is 0.130 which is significant at 0.05 level of significance. The result shows positive correlation between locality and stream. Thus, locality increases similarly the stream also

increases. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. After Statistical analysis, the investigator found the following results. There exists positive correlation between management and gender, management and stream and locality and stream. There exists negative correlation between management and locality, gender and locality and gender and stream.

V. CONCLUSION

The new digital media encompasses all aspects of youth's social lives. Young people use new media to express and explore their identities, communicate with their parents and maintain a constant connection with their peer groups. In the realm of selfhood, we see that the affordances of new digital media are well-suited to children's and adolescents' developmental needs. The activities offered in virtual worlds like Neopets allow children to express themselves in concrete ways, while the flexibility of new media technology provides adolescents with unprecedented opportunities to experiment with their identities. In the realm of family life, it is apparent that new digital media play an integral role in many current households. The socio-economic development is an essential requirement for undergraduates' future life. They are becoming increasingly important due to the reasons such as limitation of financial support, basic amenities and difficulty in obtaining upto date information, which may affect performance at examinations and work after graduation. The present study contributes to the socio-economic development through welfare scheme among undergraduates in the Kancheepuram district. The factors identified during the present study could be used to improve their socio-economic status amongst undergraduates in Kancheepuram district and other developing districts in TamilNadu with similar student populations. In addition, technology is advancing very rapidly and it is possible that some of these students are using devices and resources that are not being captured in the current survey. With respect to parental authority in adolescence, the researchers have identified the new ways that adolescent rebellion is carried out with new digital media and considered how they complicate parents' attempts to establish and exert their authority. The instantaneous, constant, and simultaneous nature of their new media communications increases opportunities for self-disclosure, with potential positive effects on levels of intimacy and perspective-taking in personal and social development. At the same time, the "hyper connectivity" afforded by the new digital media may negatively affect youth's ability to develop an independent emotional life. Moreover, the public nature of peer group membership complicates the way these peer interactions are experienced. As researchers begin to answer these questions empirically, the knowledge they generate will provide guidance for parents and educators as they continue their efforts to support the healthy development of today's youth.

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